

THE LINGUISTIC-RHETORICAL METHOD OF ADVERTISING RESEARCH: COMMONPLACES AS THE BASIS FOR THE INVENTION OF THE TEXT

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Abstract: *The article explores advertising text is a communicative unit with a special structural and semantic organization. The objectives of the study are to identify the compositional, linguistic and rhetorical parameters of this text, as well as to study the impact on the mass addressee using cognitive, pragmatic and rhetorical strategies, tactics and techniques. In this article, among the linguistic and stylistic techniques and means of expression existing in the English language, it will highlight those that, according to our analysis of the texts of English-language advertising, are characteristic of authentic advertising texts in English.*

Key words: *Evaluative and expressive vocabulary, advertising texts; metaphor, epithet, phraseological stylistic techniques, antithesis, linguistic, rhetorical*

Introduction. Today, in conditions of fierce market competition, for the active movement of their goods and services, companies strive to ensure that their advertising messages differ from others and represent the advertised brand in a favorable light. The purpose of any advertising campaign, as already noted above, is to have an emotional impact on potential consumers and make the target audience remember the message, which will eventually change the consumer attitudes of a potential buyer due to the impact of advertising on his thinking, feelings and behavior.

To realize the goals and functions of advertising, its creators use various language tools. The study of mass media texts in general and English-language advertising texts in particular has a long tradition. Many well-known scientists have occupied many questions related to the functioning of language in the field of mass media. Various aspects of advertising texts were studied using the methods of discourse analysis, content analysis, cognitive linguistics, as well as in such relatively new areas as critical linguistics and linguocultural studies. However, a detailed description of

advertising texts is hardly possible without a systematic philological analysis, which allows us to consider the text as an integral multilevel phenomenon that exists in close connection with oral and media characteristics. Texts are studied from different points of view: typological descriptions, functional style, media format, syntagmatic features, as well as from the point of view of cognitive and pragmatic approaches. Such a system of coordinated analysis allows not only to carefully analyze the individual properties of media texts, but also to output all data into a single logically structured map that best reflects their real properties and attributes.

Research Methodology . Speech, as a form of human communication, can have a very strong emotional effect on a person. V. G. Zazykin studied the methods of suggestion used in psychology and noted that some of them deserve to be used in advertising. For example, the use of words that have a specific unambiguous meaning significantly increases the power of suggestion. For example, "night", "scissors", "rose", "spicy", etc. Abstract concepts, on the contrary, reduce the effect of suggestion (Zazykin, 2002). M. Eisenberg, in turn, believes that the two most impressive, and therefore effective words in advertising are "new" and "free" and all their variations. At the same time, M. Eisenberg warns about the negative impact of a number of words, which, in his opinion, are aggressive and can cause negative emotions. These are words like "dear", "love", "fear", "child", "dark", "black", "dirty" (Eisenberg, 1993). David Ogilvy, in turn, emphasizes the need to inform the buyer of new information about the product. He notes that the following words and expressions are most often found in English-language advertising: "Now", "Amazing", "Suddenly", "Announcing", "Introducing", "It is here", "Improved", "Revolutionary", "Just arrived", "Important", "Development" (Ogilvy, 2012). Thus, it can be concluded that it is important for English-language advertising to find a specific and imaginative definition of a product characteristic for its success in advertising.

Analysis and results. In this article, among the linguistic and stylistic techniques and means of expression existing in the English language, it will highlight those that, according to our analysis of the texts of English-language advertising, are characteristic of authentic advertising texts in English.

1. Evaluative and expressive vocabulary.

As a result of the conducted research, we came to the conclusion that the evaluative and expressive lexicon always emphasizes the attractive qualities of the advertised product, often even exaggerating its

incorruptibility and thereby imposing on the recipient a deliberately overestimated opinion about it. As an example, it is possible to advertise decorative cosmetics, in particular, the lipstick of the company "Lancome": Absolutely Lancome Absolutely luxurious colour. Absolutely versatile from classic crèmeto, richest matte to the irresistible hint of sheen in new Matte Lustre.

In the above example of advertising, we can observe the repeated use of the adverb "absolutely", emphasizing the exclusivity of the phrase, and the superlative degree of the adjective "richest", creating the impression of the maximum severity of this characteristic. In general, after considering such examples, we noted the exceptionally frequent use of such lexemes as "absolutely" and "best" in English-language advertising texts.

2. Epithet

Epithets are another group of lexemes that give an advertising message an evaluative coloring. By definition, an epithet is a word or expression that makes a word more colorful, saturated. Almost all advertising in English includes the most diverse epithets. For example, an English-language Coca-Cola ad: "Calm, Cool and Collectable". The use of phrasal epithets adds brightness and contrast to the product. For example, the advertising medium for the Lens is Complete: "Finally, lens wearers shave a solution for end-of-day dryness". I would like to note that the greatest number of portraits can be found in the advertising of goods for women, namely, cosmetic products, which is most likely due to the psychological characteristics of women's thinking, emotionality of perception.

3. Pun (pun on words)

A pun is a figure of speech consisting in the humorous (parody) use of different meanings of the same word or two similar-sounding words. The wordplay in the advertising text always arouses interest and is easier to remember by the recipient, thus contributing to consumer activity. "For some the essence is to see, for others to see the essence" (For some the main thing is to see, for others—to see the main thing). This slogan of Pilsner Urquell beer uses a pun: the word "essence" has a different meaning; the latter emphasizes the peculiarity of the brand—focus on people who look deeper into the essence of things than others. Maybe she's born with it, maybe it's Maybelline (Maybe she was born that way, or maybe it's all Maybelline). In this example, the similarity of the sound of the word "maybe" is played and the names of the cosmetics brand "Maybelline". A

pun can not only intrigue the buyer, but also, with the help of a humorous effect, cause positive emotions and, accordingly, pleasant associations with the product. A vivid example of this use of a pun is seen in the following advertisement for Scotch whiskey "Walt Scotch Whiskey": "This is a work of art inside a work of art".

4. Phraseological stylistic techniques.

Phraseological stylistic techniques – associative series, in other words, key images that are important for the bearers of a certain culture, are fixed, in particular, in the form of proverbs. The use of phraseological stylistic techniques in advertising can both increase its effectiveness and have the opposite effect, if the phraseology is chosen and used incorrectly, that is, it does not fit the product being advertised. Therefore, we can talk about the ambiguity of this technique. Successful, in our opinion, can be called the use of the phraseological phrase "to be in somebody's shoes" ("to be in someone's place") in the advertising of Reebok sneakers: "Millions of girls want to be in her shoes. But she wants to be in ours". The famous singer and dancer Paola Abdul advertised this product. In the first sentence, the expression "to be in somebody's shoes" is used in relation to Paola Abdul, who is admired by thousands of fans. In the second sentence, the phrase "she wants to be in ours" should be understood in its literal sense, that is, the dancer herself chooses Reebok shoes for herself. Another example is the advertisement of the liqueur "Grand Marinier": "One good turn deserves another". In the example considered, the use of the well-known English phrase "One good turn deserves another" ("What you sow, you reap", "As you, so to you") allows you to achieve a humorous effect, since the word "turn" in this case means another contrast.

5. Metaphor

A metaphor is a turn of speech in which, based on some similarity of two objects, words and expressions are used in a figurative sense. A metaphor not only forms an idea of an object, but also offers a certain way of thinking about it. The metaphor used in advertising is characterized by brevity and conciseness. Its purpose is to name objects and phenomena figuratively, expressively and easily. For example: "Smart money knows where to go". (CITIBANK advertising) "Tchibo. Awaken the Senses". (advertisement for the coffee Shop) "Engineered to move the human spirit". (Mercedes-Benz car advertisement) "Lee. The jeans that built America". (Lee Jeans advertisement)

In the examples given, we see a successful application of an advertising metaphor to create an appropriate image of the advertised

product, since the advertising metaphor allows us to consider some products through the properties and qualities of others. It creates an original advertising image and brings an evaluation element to the text of the advertising message.

6. Comparisons

Comparison is a stylistic device based on the figurative transformation of a grammatically formed comparison. Comparisons are often used in advertising texts, so we will look at comparisons in more detail in our work. There are the following ways of grammatical design of the comparison: a) comparative turnover; b) the comparative degree of an adjective or adverb. For example, an advertisement for an Internet site in a magazine: "It's not as big a leap as you think". Or an advertisement for Nopeu-Comb cornflakes: "It's the most fabulous party of the year...". Catbury chocolate chip cookies advertisement: "The best chocolate biscuits, because they are covered in the best chocolate".

According to advertising researchers, comparisons that are incorrect from a logical point of view are superficial manifestations of one deep phenomenon of manipulation. The absence of real distinctive properties of the product, favorably distinguishing it from numerous competitors' products, forces advertisers to look for special rhetorical techniques. These techniques are able to actualize in the mind of a potential buyer such a comparison class and such comparison parameters, against which the advertised product looks the most advantageous. For example, the slogan of Duracell: "No battery is stronger longer".

7. Pronouns

Personal and possessive pronouns of the second person are often used in advertising texts, because they strengthen the advertising appeal. For example: "Your own car. Your own phone. Your own place. Your dad's insurance?" (Nationwide Insurance company advertisement) "Your friends will want to look at it. You won't even want to take it off to shower. Years later, babies will want to touch its light. Little girls will ask to try it on. And long after everything has changed, you'll look down at it and realize nothing has". (De Beers Diamond Engagement Ring advertisement)

8. Antithesis

The antithesis can also be attributed to the lexical means of expressiveness of the advertising text. It can be characterized as a connection and opposition of opposite concepts, images, ideas in order to achieve greater clarity, as well as for a more vivid expression of feelings and ideas. As a result of using the antithesis, a contrast effect is achieved, and

the advertising message acquires a more original sound, and the value is determined more accurately due to comparison with its opposite value. The antithesis is widely used in advertising headlines, for example, in the advertising of the PEUGEOT 106 car: "Espaceinterieur maximum. Encombrement minimum". Thus, having analyzed the linguistic and stylistic techniques and means of expression used in English-language advertising, we can conclude that the linguistic and stylistic features of the advertising text are directly related to the pragmatic task set by the address. The advertising text is a complete message with a clearly defined pragmatic attitude (attracting attention to the advertised product), combining the signs of written and oral speech with a number of extralinguistic means. In advertising texts, the impact function is most fully represented, implemented with the help of the entire arsenal of linguistic and stylistic means.

Since the purpose of advertising is an intense impact on the recipient, a rich arsenal of means of expression is used in the advertising text at all language levels. In particular, syntactic and morpho-syntactic means of expressiveness are widely represented in the English language text messages. In this chapter, we analyze exactly these features of advertising texts.

Thus, it can be concluded that syntactic techniques and means of expression are widely used in advertising texts, which serve as additional means of highlighting and enhancing cognitive components. The syntax of the advertising message, along with the lexical content, largely determines the strength of its impact on the potential buyer.

Conclusion/Recommendations.

In print advertising, verbal metaphors are mostly used as captions, taglines or slogans for the product. Although the present study does not focus on print advertising.

Future studies could assess the impact and effectiveness of visual and verbal metaphors in this context. This research also presents grounds for future research into the application of visual metaphor in sundry other industries and sectors, including education, healthcare, manufacturing, and more.

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